
**IMPROVEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC AND
METHODOLOGICAL BASE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST IN
PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Abstract

This article presents the scientific and methodological basis for the development of interest in physical education and sports among school teachers

Key words

Methods, aspects, theories, teaching methods, physical education, teacher.

Physical education is a pedagogical process, the peculiarity of which is to teach movement and education of a person's physical condition. In applied terms, public education is a process of physical preparation of a person for socially conditioned activity.

In order to determine whether the tuning method is a tuning process, it is necessary to specify four main tuning criteria for it. Maximum results in the development of knowledge, skills and abilities, minimum time and teachers to achieve sufficient learning goals. Minimal use of the trend to achieve the set results in the current time interval. The minimum way to achieve the set results in the current time interval.

The basic concepts in the field of physical culture include the following: "Physical culture", "Physical education", "Sport", "Physical development", "Physical improvement", "Physical training", "Physical education". Physical culture is a type of culture of a person and society. The concept of "Physical balance" is associated with the concepts of human movements and motor actions. Movement as a motor function of the body is a change in the view of the body or its parts in the direction of moving objects or to each other. Movements can be arbitrary and involuntary.

Physical culture is a part of the culture of society, which is a set of values and knowledge that create and apply society for the physical and intellectual

development of human abilities, which leads to his motor activity and the formation of a healthy lifestyle, social evolution.

Dynamic exercises are exercises that predict the performance of a movement with the body in a balanced position.

In the content of a person's physical culture, it includes socially formed physical abilities of a person associated with their knowledge, interests, creative, value orientations, as well as the development of personal means of preserving and manifesting these abilities.

Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the forms and properties of the human body, the engine of the formation of skills, skills related to their knowledge and the development of physical qualities. The main means of physical education are physical exercises. Physical education is the basis for a comprehensive and defining personal development. This is inextricably linked with intelligence: in order to work mentally, it is necessary to expend a certain amount of physical strength. Physical development is not only a strengthening of the will, but also an increase in the strength of a small person. There are five main qualities: strength, endurance, speed, flexibility, agility. Sport is a special generic physical or intellectual activity that can be achieved for the purpose of competitions, as well as purposeful preparation for them by warming up, training. Physical perfection - In the generally accepted understanding is the objective essence of physical culture, which is the result of the purposeful formation of a developed human body. Physical development is a change in the process, as well as a set of morphological properties and properties of the organism. Physical development is the process of changing the forms and functions of the body under the influence of conditions or the purposeful use of special physical exercises. Physical exercises are the main means of protecting all types of physical culture. Physical culture is an idea from the 90s of the 19th century, introduced in England and the USA. In Russia, the term came in 1908-1910. These formulations meant: public education of people, education and ensuring their health.

Conclusion: Physical qualities are innate qualities that help us move. The category of such qualities includes speed, endurance, strength, agility, flexibility. Speed is a person's ability to perform maximum movements to create time segments. This is a very important quality for any person.

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